

**TECHNOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS FOR DEVELOPING
COGNITIVE-METHODOLOGICAL COMPETENCE OF
FUTURE TEACHERS IN TEACHING PHILOSOPHY**

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the theoretical aspects of developing cognitive-methodological competence of future teachers, the methodology for developing cognitive-methodological competence of future teachers, the effectiveness of developing cognitive-methodological competence of future teachers. The theoretical and methodological basis for developing cognitive-methodological competence of future teachers is also analyzed.

Introduction. Improving the technological foundations and modernizing the system for developing the cognitive-methodological competence of future teachers in teaching philosophy is one of the most important and urgent pedagogical tasks.

A technological approach to the pedagogical process aimed at developing the cognitive-methodological competence of future teachers is a systematic process focused on clarifying the goals and objectives of the pedagogical process based on its outcomes, designing each stage of the process separately, and clearly defining its forms, methods, and tools.

Literature review and methods.

The theoretical aspects of developing the cognitive-methodological competence of future teachers, the methodology for its development, and the effectiveness of this process have been studied by scholars such as T. Buzan, N. German, M. Bernis, M. Pietra, E. Terhart, R. Dunn, M. Akhmetov, A. Bazayeva, L. Bocharova, E. Vyazovova, T. Dobridina, I. Dulchayeva, E. Zeyer, T. Korotenko, L. Osipova, A. Piligin, V. Pustovoytov, S. Roslyakova, U. Inoyatov, N. Muslimov, O. Musurmonova, B. Khodjayev, M. Vakhobov, and M. Mirsoliyeva.

Results and discussion.

The analysis of philosophical, sociological, psychological, and pedagogical literature shows that reflection manifests as an integral component of learning to think, self-knowledge, communication, self-awareness, and self-education, as well as of knowledge acquisition and the educational process as a whole. The idea of a reflective approach in developing students' cognitive-methodological competence enables its application both in the learning process and in extracurricular activities.

Reflection is understood as the ability of students to think in ways directed toward understanding and comprehending the structure of cognitive-methodological competence, as well as the personal forms and conditions of its development. The study of theoretical and practical research made it possible to develop a technology for fostering students' cognitive-methodological competence. The main objective of this technology is to cultivate a value-based attitude toward the teaching profession based on cognitive-methodological competence and to develop the ability to freely choose personally and socially meaningful orientations.

The technology consists of four components:

Theoretical-methodological: goals, objectives, and principles for forming a humanistic orientation in future teachers;

Content-based: the humanistic content implemented through the triad "knowledge – values – activity";

Procedural: the system of the teacher's activities in the educational process based on reflective methods and techniques;

Evaluative: indicators, levels, and criteria for assessing their effectiveness.

The methodological foundations of the technology are based on relational, axiological, cultural, subject-oriented, and activity-based principles, as well as on the principles of integrity and systemacity within the framework of humanistic pedagogy.

The content and procedural components of the technology, the description of the process of developing cognitive-methodological competence in future teachers, and the level of manifestation of reflection are reflected in the technological map as criteria of the studied process.

In teaching the course "*Philosophy*," a number of methods of educational activity are known. Based on different classifications of methods, we consider the implementation of a cultural-humanistic approach in education to be associated with the following methods:

Verbal (influencing consciousness): narration, working with books, explanation, verbal persuasion, comparison, answering questions, discussions on ethics, discussing prospects, approval or disapproval;

Socio-pedagogical (environmental-pedagogical influence): encouragement, organizing prospects, rules of conduct, rituals, traditions, figurative representation, participation in collaborative work, creating a cohesive team environment, competitions (individual and group), group control, collective opinion, harmonious group atmosphere, reports, meetings, discussion and evaluation of achievements, providing support and assistance to peers, pedagogical teams, and mentors;

Activity-based (practical influence): formation of moral behavior, creation of educational situations, educational work (socially useful activities such as helping the sick, elderly, and disabled, environmental protection, working with juvenile offenders, participation in community service activities, artistic creativity, etc.), practical problem-solving, discipline, practicing good manners, social assignments, activity modeling, modeling internal (psychological) difficulties, overcoming challenges and failures, jointly searching for solutions, relying on experience, requirements, training, self-training, participation in joint activities, helping others, supporting peers and the community, developing collective

interdependent behavior, gaining experience, psycho-pedagogical testing of educational outcomes, the “self-method”;

Planning-oriented: structuring, activation, regulation, modeling activities, selecting forms of pedagogical interaction;

Organizational: organizing the group and its self-governance bodies, coordinating collective activities, distributing roles, guiding and managing students’ responsibility;

Mobilizing-informational: presenting significant goals, social-subjective experience, psychological states, motivational activities and behavior, psychological support, guidance and advice;

Communicative: defining key positions, regulating relationships and developing their norms, gradually increasing mutual responsibility, fostering trust and cooperation;

Coordinating-corrective: organizing students and educational activities, developing and selecting requirements for correcting actions and efforts.

In connection with these methods, the types of student activities in the implementation of a philosophical approach have also been identified: satisfying broad cultural interests in various fields of cultural activity; goal-oriented and self-directed learning; continuous engagement with art; independent study of key humanistic sources (philosophy, ethics, aesthetics, ecology); understanding diverse forms of artistic creativity and personal interests, increasing interest in reading, participation in artistic activities, developing aesthetic taste through organizing exhibitions and competitions; socio-pedagogical aspects of students’ cognitive activity—analysis and comparison of acquired information, ability to foresee personal activity and possible difficulties, and the wide implementation of psychological-pedagogical training that enables modeling pedagogical situations, and others.

Based on the above, in designing educational technologies for the course “*Philosophy of Knowledge*,” the following key conceptual approaches should be taken into account:

Learner-centered education. By its nature, this approach ensures the full development of all participants in the educational process. While complying with the requirements of state educational standards, it is not limited to focusing on the learner’s level of intellectual development, but also involves taking into account their psychological, professional, and personal characteristics.

Systemic approach. Educational technology must embody all the characteristics of a system: the logical coherence of the process, the interconnection of its components, and its integrity.

Practical approach. This approach focuses on directing the educational process toward developing practical skills and work-related qualities in the individual. It requires the activation and intensification of students’ activity, ensuring the full utilization of their abilities, capabilities, attentiveness, and initiative in the learning process.

Dialogic approach. This approach emphasizes the need to establish psychological unity and cooperation among the participants of the educational process. As a result, the learner’s creative activity and self-expression are enhanced.

Organization of collaborative learning. This approach is based on the principles of democracy and equality, ensuring equal subject–subject relations between teacher and student, as well as the joint determination of goals and the content of activities.

Problem-based approach. This is one of the methods of activating collaboration with students by presenting the learning process through problem situations. It ensures the identification of objective contradictions in scientific knowledge and the development of dialectical thinking through solving them, as well as their creative application in practical activities.

CONCLUSION. Modern research has clarified that cognitive activity is closely linked with practical needs, the management of cognitive processes, the facilitation of learning through cognitive skills, and the intensive use of information technologies. The discipline of general theoretical issues of philosophy occupies an important place in analyzing the problems of existence, development, and cognition. It also plays a significant role in examining issues such as the theory of knowledge, the relationship between sensory and logical cognition, empiricism and rationality, the problem of truth in scientific knowledge, the interconnection between theory and practice, the scientific worldview and its evolution, and the philosophical foundations of generating new knowledge.

The experience of implementing facilitative conditions in education has shown a strong positive impact on increasing learners' activity in setting clear goals and objectives, intensifying learning motivation, enhancing responsibility and independence, activating reflective activity, and improving both the effectiveness of education and discipline.

References:

- [1] McCarthy, Bernice. *About Teaching: 4MAT in the Classroom*. Wauconda, IL: About Learning, 2000..
- [2] Alekseev, N.G., and Semenov, I.N. *Methodological Analysis of the Structure of Ergonomic Knowledge: Abstracts of Reports of the IV International Conference of CMEA Member Countries on Ergonomics*. Moscow, 1998.
- [3] Baturin, N.A., Bashkatov, S.A., and Gafarova, N.V. *Theoretical Model of Personal Well-Being*. *Bulletin of South Ural State University. Series "Psychology,"* 2013.
- [4] Rogers, C. *A Way of Being (On Psychotherapy: Becoming a Person)*. Moscow: Progress, 1994.
- [5] McCarthy B. *About Teaching: 4MAT in the Classroom*. – Wauconda, IL: About Learning, 2000. – 240 p.
- [6] Alekseev N.G., Semenov I.N. *Methodological Analysis of the Structure of Ergonomic Knowledge: Abstracts of Reports of the IV International Conference of CMEA Member Countries on Ergonomics*. – Moscow, 1998. – 156 p.
- [7] Baturin N.A., Bashkatov S.A., Gafarova N.V. *Theoretical Model of Personal Well-Being*. // *Bulletin of South Ural State University. Psychology Series*. – 2013. – No. 4. – Pp. 12–18.
- [8] Rogers C. *On Psychotherapy: The Development of a Person*. – Moscow: Progress, 1994. – 480 p.
- [9] Vygotsky L.S. *Thought and Language*. – Moscow: Pedagogika, 1999. – 352 p.
- [10] Davydov V.V. *Theory of Developmental Learning*. – Moscow: Integral, 1996. – 544 p.
- [11] Zeer E.F. *Psychology of Professional Education*. – Moscow: Akademiya, 2003. – 336 p.
- [12] Muslimov N.A. *Theory and Practice of Professional Competence Formation*. – Tashkent: Fan, 2010. – 280 p.
- [13] Inoyatov U.I. *Educational Management*. – Tashkent: O'qituvchi, 2012. – 256 p.

[14] Khodjaev B.Kh. Pedagogical Technologies and Pedagogical Mastery. – Tashkent: Fan, 2015. – 300 p.

[15] Musurmonova O.A. Innovative Technologies in Education. – Tashkent: Iqtisodiyot, 2018. – 220 p.

